

THE CHANGING ROLE OF WOMEN IN URBAN TRANSPORT SYSTEM: A STUDY ON FEMALE COMMERCIAL TRICYCLE RIDERS IN LOKOJA METROPOLIS, 2001-2021

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Abstract: *Transportation system in Nigeria is majorly occupied by the male gender and has given little or no opportunity for the female gender to be involved. Women are believed to be care givers and are seen not to be fit for the job. Women who have interest in the occupation cannot take up the occupation because of the societal stereotype, because commercial transportation business has hitherto been ascribed to the male gender alone, thereby making many women who have interest in it to remain unemployed and unable to engage themselves in the career of their choice. With the advent of civilization and globalization there has been a changing role of women in most sectors of work force. This change also applies to the transport sector. The study examines the changing role of women in the transport sector with reference to the tricycle subsector by focusing on the female tricycle riders in Lokoja metropolis. The study adopted the historical methodology and relied on the use of both primary and secondary data in the presentation of the narrative. The study concludes that women have contributed to the urban transport system in Lokoja through their involvement in commercial tricycle riding, a business sector hitherto dominated by men. This paradigm shift demonstrated clearly that women are not petrified to take up new roles in the development of the society. Therefore, women should be encouraged to contribute their quota to the growth and development of the society in every sector of the economy.*

Introduction

Lokoja, is a town that has been existing since the pre-colonial era and currently the capital of Kogi

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

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State. Due to its location in the Middle Belt of the country and on the confluence of the Rivers Niger and Benue, it served as a rendezvous for traders from different parts of Nigeria during the pre-colonial period and as transit station for many trans-nationals from the different parts of the world (especially the Europeans) during the colonial period. Lokoja is made up of ethnic groups such as the Oworo, the Bassa-Nge, the Nupe, among others. However, it has currently become a multi-ethnic town due to its strategic location, the colonial-activities during the colonial era and new developments. Lokoja serves as a gateway city that strategically links many urban cities to the north, south, east and west of the country, hence it plays a major role in the transport system.¹

Transportation is the movement of goods and persons from place to place and the various means by which such movement is accomplished. The growth of the ability and the need to transport large quantities of goods or numbers of people over long distances at high speed in comfort and safety has been an index of civilization and in particular of technological

progress.² It has always been an important activity of man from the most primitive to the most advanced states. Transportation is also crucial to the development of any nation because of its impact on social, political and economic activities.³ The role and impact of transportation on man cannot be overemphasized.

Gender on the other hand, refers to the economic, social, political and cultural attributes and opportunities associated with being women and men. The social definitions of what it means to be a man or woman vary among cultures and change over time. Gender is a sociocultural expression of particular characteristics and roles that are associated with certain groups of people with reference to their sex and sexuality.⁴ Gender roles vary in different societies. While men and women have equal rights and opportunities in some, men dominate in others and rarely do women control the administration of a community, religious positions and certain field of work. Also, in high masculinity societies, like Nigeria, women have restricted opportunities in vocations or societal hierarchy.⁵ These restrictions, faced by women especially

¹ Anthony Danladi Ali, *Trade and Transport in the Lower Niger 1830-2011* (Lagos: Adenuga Concept, 2012), 44-60.

² The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, www.britannica.com/technology/transportation Accessed September 20, 2021.

³ Anthony Danladi Ali, *Trade and Transport in the Lower Niger 1830-2011* (Lagos: Adenuga Concept, 2012), 15.

⁴ Gender Concept and Definitions www.GenderDefinition/Concept Accessed September 20, 2021.

⁵ Kathleen Gerson, *The Unfinished Revolution: How a New Generation is Reshaping, Family, Work and Gender in America* (London: Oxford University Press, 2009), 31.

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concerning the case study of this work which is transportation, has brought about certain set back in economic development, as the involvement of women in the transportation system can bring about increase in labour force and economic development.

There are various modes of transport system in Nigeria. These modes of transport system, comprises of the road transport system, the water transport system, the rail transport system and the air transport system. However, this research work shall be focusing on the road transport system with major emphasis on tricycle. The introduction of tricycle into Nigeria was necessitated by constant and alarming rate of the commercial motorcycle accident and the quest to provide employment for youths, provide micro-credit and to eradicate poverty across Nigeria by President Obasanjo's administration. Prior to this time, the government has tried to ban the operation of commercial motorcycle but did not succeed and hence, led to the emergence of tricycle (Keke-NAPEP) under the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP). Tricycles are filling the huge gaps that presently exist in the Nigerian transportation sector. They are still a very popular mode of transportation in Nigeria today. Thus, tricycle (Keke-NAPEP)

business is one aspect of transportation that is booming right now. As the population of Nigeria keep increasing day by day, the need to transport and move people from one place to the other is also on the rise.⁶

A popular saying goes that what a man can do, a woman can do better. In an average Nigerian society, due to certain cultural and traditional limitations, some vocations are believed to be masculine inclined and prohibited to the female gender. Nevertheless, with the advent of civilization and the evolvement of time, women have started engaging themselves in these vocations believed to be meant solely for the male gender and some are even excelling and doing better at their vocations. In Nigeria, the transportation system is believed to be of the male gender and is majorly occupied by them. Though, in recent times, women are now involving themselves in the transport system and has also taken it up as an occupation. We now have women who have taken up the riding of tricycles (Keke-NAPEP) as an occupation.

The transformation of gender relations since the beginning of the 20th century, is one of the most rapid profound social changes in human history. Even at the beginning of the 20th century, men and women were generally viewed as occupying

⁶ Memud Jeremiah Oluwaseun, *A Historical Assessment of Keke Napep (Tricycle) in Urban Transformation: A Case Study*

of Lokoja, 2001-2018. (Unpublished BA Project Department of History and International Studies, FUL, 2019), 7.

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

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sharply different roles in the society: a woman's place was in the home, as a wife and mother; the man's place was in the public sphere. By the 21st century, only a small minority of people still hold to the view that women should be subordinate to men. While all sorts of gender inequalities continue to exist and some of these seem resistant to change, these exist in a completely different context of cultural norms, political and social rights and institutionalized rules and male domination has not disappeared, but it is on the defensive and its foundations are crumbling.⁷ The 21st century came with a landmark of civilization which has greatly changed the view of the world concerning the role of women in the society. How women have now taken advantage of opportunities has undermined certain traditional patterns of gender relations.

It is in the light of the above that this research shall be examining the evolution and changing role of women in the transport system with the special focus on women tricycle riders in Lokoja. Thus, interrogating the nature of urban transport system in Lokoja before the advent of tricycle in Lokoja and the level of involvement of women in the urban transport system in Lokoja and the impact and challenges of women's

involvement in the urban transport system, especially, the tricycle sub sector.

Literature Review

John Coyle et al in their book *Transportation; A Supply Chain Perspective*,⁸ examined the importance of transportation to economy in the aspect of supply chain and a critical link of transportation to supply chain management in the United States. According to John, et all, the net impact is that transportation can no longer be taken for granted as its importance to the efficient and effectiveness of supply chains is significant and increasing. Transportation is an important and pervasive element in our society that affects every person either directly or indirectly, the goods we consume, our economic livelihoods, our mobility, and our entertainment are impacted by transportation and even the growth of a nation's economy is inherent in transportation. The work also examines the role of transportation in the movement of people and the influence of such movement has on population centers and businesses and how transportation adds value to a product. Therefore, this research seeks to fill the gap in this work by focusing on Nigeria with much emphasis on tricycle in Lokoja.

⁷ Erik Olin, *Contemporary American Society* (New York: W.W Norton and Company, 2015), 81.

⁸ John Coyle et al, *Transportation; A Supply Chain Perspective*, (United States: South Western College Publishing, 2003)

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

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According to Jibrilla Hamza Modibbo and Fashola Opeyemi Mary in their article “Impact of Commercial Tricycle Operators on Income of Youth in Mubi North Local Government, Adamawa State Nigeria”⁹ noted that universally tricycle is seen as a subsector in land transportation, and transportation is a critical factor for sustained economic growth and modernization of a nation. The adequacy of this vital infrastructure is an important determinant of the successive growth of the nation’s income. An effort in diversifying its production base, expanding trade linking resources and markets into an integrated economy will lead to rapid increase in the G.D.P. Historically, peoples’ capacity to move around was restricted because the prevailing mode of transportation has been animal and water, improvement in land and air bone transportation have accelerated the abilities of people to travel long distance in shorter time. The writers examined human-powered trikes and motorized trikes. Human-powered trikes are powered by pedals or hand cranks, motorized trikes can be powered by motorcycle engines, smaller automatic transmission scooter motors, or electric motors and how in 1789, two French investors developed

a three wheeled vehicle, powered by pedals; called the tricycle. Nowadays, tricycle is seen as the major intra-city commercial transport system in the urban cities of the country, especially cities where commercial motorcycles were restricted and banned from operation, as such an anatomy of aspects relating to insecurity and increased level of mortal accidents due to reckless motorcycle riders and inadequate transportation networks in the country. Investment in transportation infrastructure is critical to sustained standard of living as well as economic growth and development. Mobility studies show that transportation is essential to economic productivity and remains competitive in the global economy. The writers also examined how the ban of commercial motorcycle has left many jobless and how the former motorcycle riders and many others turn to tricycle riding business and buses to cushion the effects of the unemployment. They further noted that the problems of insecurity, poverty and unemployment in Nigeria was alarming at a time and in response, the government formulated and generated strategies, programmes and policies aiming at the alleviation and reduction of poverty and unemployment thereby introducing

⁹ Jibrilla Hamza Modibbo and Fashola Opeyemi Mary, “Impact of Commercial Tricycle Operators on Income of Youth in Mubi North Local Government,

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

Adamawa State, Nigeria” IDOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science, 2, 2017, 56-72.

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the National Poverty Alleviation Program (NAPEP) where tricycles were distributed across the nation under President Olusegun Obasanjo. This current study is focused on the changing role of women in the urban transportation system by focusing on female commercial tricycle riders in Lokoja.

Igwe C.N et al in their work, “A Review: Nigeria’s Transport System and the Place of Entrepreneurs”¹⁰ noted that transportation is a requirement for every nation, regardless of its industrial capacity, population size or technological development. They also noted that the Nigerian transport systems, right from inception, were poorly designed and unable to scale up to meet greater demands, a design flaw which causes traffic congestion on roads, overstressed railways, faltering airfields and mass-transport blind spots. The paper discusses the origins of modern Nigerian transportation, problems in its transportation infrastructure and system, and emphasizes the role of entrepreneurship as the strategic instrument for creating an effective transportation system conducive to business and then makes policy

suggestions, after considering the potentials of moving goods and people from one place to another, which is critical to maintain strong economic and political ties between regions in the country. With a land area of 910,768 sq. km, population estimate of over 150 million people and GDP-growth rate of 6% per annum (2006 est), the centrality of effective public transportation in Nigeria is readily seen.

Ibrahim A. Jawondo and Roseline Oshewolo in their article “From Empowerment to Disempowerment? The Changing Role of Women in the Colonial Agricultural Economy of Okunland, Kogi State, Nigeria”¹¹ examined the changing role of women in the agricultural economy of Okunland occasioned by the transition from the pre-colonial arrangement to colonization. Opinions are divided in the literature on the gendered processes in relation to colonial agricultural economy in most of Africa. The first thinking is that women lost power and economic autonomy as a result of discriminatory colonial policies. The second thinking suggest that the residual role of women in the agricultural economy was a product of

¹⁰ Igwe C.N et al, “A Review: Nigeria’s Transportation System and the Place of Entrepreneurs, *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*” 3, 2013, 168-179.

¹¹ Ibrahim A. Jawondo and Roseline Oshewolo, “From Empowerment to Disempowerment? The Changing Role of Women in the Colonial Agricultural Economy of Okunland, Kogi State, Nigeria” *Geo Journal* 2020, 1-14.

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

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choice rather than a deliberate colonial policy. The third maintains that women were economically active and productive but were unable to claim the proceeds of their labour. The authors also examined how that in Okunland, while women were prominently involved in the agricultural economy in the pre-colonial period, they appeared to be relegated to playing a residual role during the colonial period, leading to disempowerment. And how that the residual role played by women in the agricultural economy of colonial Okunland could be attributed to British colonial economic policies which generally favoured the men.

The writers noted that in African countries, the subject of women has emerged as an issue of major national and international significance, principally because of the delineation of women as the neglected dimension in the continent's development. Feminist issues therefore do not only represent a major source of media interest; newspapers also frequently publish stories about how political behavior has marginalized women's participation and empowerment. In Nigeria, in particular, women are demanding to be heard by questioning men's dominance over them as well as the values and idea that support such male dominance and like in other African societies, the overwhelming body of literature has described the Nigerian society as historically patriarchal. The authors also examined the

different roles of men and women in agriculture before the colonial era and how things changed when Okunland came under the British rule. The British Colonial economic policies in Okunland and elsewhere in Nigeria were necessitated by the increasing demand for markets and raw material for their industries back home. It is in this regard that agriculture was expanded. These policies also promoted the production of cash crops. The colonial government trained more men on techniques of improving production and improved varieties were introduced to men, leaving out the women. The implication was that men dominated the cash crop agriculture while women were forced to abandon their indigenous cotton production to take up on growing food crops for family consumption.

According to the writers, one could say that the policies were not really intended to discriminate against women but they were obviously not designed to empower them either. The cash crop-oriented colonial economy targeted the able-bodied men who could work under stressful conditions to make money and consequently pay taxes to the colonial government. Although the women still carved a niche for themselves in certain economic area but they were largely not recognized as important agents of economic development as was the case in the pre-colonial era. Women were therefore relegated to a position of inconsequence in agriculture. Just as

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

the authors in this journal examined the changing roles of women in the agricultural sector, the current research examines the changing role of women in the transportation sector, narrowing it down to female commercial tricycle riders in Lokoja, Kogi state.

According to Ekundayo Aduke in her article “Women in Pre-Colonial Economic Development in North East Yoruba Land of Nigeria”¹² examined how that in the indigenous society, family followed a strict division of labour based on sex and age. Each had its functions defined and they were rigidly adhered to. The author also examined how the role of women in procreation and subsistence economy cannot be underestimated. However, few written literatures exist on the role of women played in production history in Okunland. The major theme in the journal is the survey of women’s role in pre-colonial economy of North East Yorubaland (Okunland). It also highlights the various economic resources and activities engaged in by women and noted that the womenfolk indispensable in economic development. The author further explained that pre-colonial Okunland was divided along gender

line, sex was the basis of role-allocation. So economic activities were sex specific, while some were general. However, women formed a bulwark of the pre-colonial economy of the area. They were not only active in farming and processing of agricultural produce, they were very active in other sectors of economy like craft industries, clothe weaving, making of clay pots and native soaps, marketing or trading, especially in local periodic market which were exclusively dominated by women. It is arising from the above literature that this study seeks to examine gender roles as well as the contribution of women to economic development with regards to the transportation sector in Lokoja.

The Evolution of Female Tricycle Riders in Lokoja

The evolution of female tricycle riders began in the year 2016.¹³ According to the State Chairman of the Tricycle Owners Association of Nigeria (TOAN) Alhaji Idris Abdulraham, the first woman to ride a tricycle in Lokoja was Mrs. Garuba, although it was not for commercial purpose as she only rode it in order to run personal errands. Mrs. Garuba’s husband was the owner of the tricycle, it was an open back

¹² Ekundayo Aduke, “Women in Pre-Colonial Economic Development in North East Yoruba Land of Nigeria” Specialty Journal of Humanities and Cultural Science, 4, 2019, 60-64.

¹³ Interview with Alhaji Idris Abdulraham, TOAN State Chairman, 48 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

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tricycle and usually used it to convey kegs of water from the public water borehole to his house for domestic use. On a faithful day, Mr. Garuba travelled out of town, unfortunately the family was in need of water but Mrs. Garuba could not provide water for the family cause of the far distance of the public borehole and her inability to ride a tricycle. When Mr. Garuba returned, she narrated the situation to him and asked him to teach her how to ride a tricycle which he did. Subsequently, Mrs. Garuba no longer needed the help of her husband to provide water anymore as she was now skilled in tricycle riding. She then began to frequently use the tricycle to provide water for her family and she was seen doing that by many people on several occasions. This made Mrs. Garuba the first woman to ride a tricycle in Lokoja.¹⁴

However, with the massive influx of passenger tricycles and the booming rate of tricycle riding business on 2016, women started developing interest in the occupation even though it was mainly occupied by the male gender. The first woman to ever ride a tricycle for commercial purpose in Lokoja was Mrs. Aisha. She developed interest in the business and met the leaders of Tricycle Owners Association of Nigeria (TOAN) and asked to join the Association and

also take riding lessons. The Association got her registered and also took out time to take her riding lessons. The Association also aided her by recommending her to a flint owner. This gave her access to a tricycle, and started the tricycle riding business. Her participation in the parade to welcome Indian delegates from a tricycle company, made her feel accepted by the association and it encouraged her to be more active in the association.¹⁵

The involvement of Mrs. Aisha in the tricycle riding business attracted the attention of other women to the occupation. Two other women identified as Miss Blessing and Mrs. Sandra joined the Tricycle Owners Association of Nigeria. They became registered members of the association and were taught how to ride a tricycle. The association also recommended them to flint owners and they began the tricycle riding business. The Association then passed a law that stated that all female tricycle riders are exempted from paying daily dues to obtain daily tickets, they are only to pay weekly dues at the weekly meetings. This was done to help in making things easier for the female members of the association so that they can easily pay the flint owners. After Miss Blessing and Mrs. Sandra came Mrs. Success popularly known as

¹⁴ Interview with Alhaji Idris Abdulrahman, TOAN State Chairman, 48 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

¹⁵ Interview with Comrade Adamu Shehu, TOAN Deputy State Chairman, 38 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

“MAMA”. She used to be a tricycle rider in Lagos. After moving to Lokoja, she decided to continue her tricycle riding business so she joined the Tricycle Owners Association of Nigeria, Lokoja chapter. There was no need for her to undergo a riding lesson because she was already a skilled tricycle rider. She is considered by most tricycle riders to be a very skilled rider even though she is way older than all other female tricycle riders. After registering with the association, she bought a second-hand tricycle for herself and started the business. All these earned her the nickname, “MAMA”.¹⁶

Mrs. Vivian Jegede is currently the last woman to join the association in the year 2021. She is serving as the Welfare Officer of the Tricycle Owners Association of Nigeria (TOAN) Lokoja branch/State Office welfare officer. According to Mrs. Vivian, picked interest in the tricycle riding business because she saw how people were always standing to wait for tricycles at her junction every morning. She stated that there is always scarcity of tricycles in the morning so she decided to take up the business in order to help in the little way she can by conveying people to their place of work, school or market place. She stated that she enjoys the work because she can

resume and close at any time of her choice and she can also take breaks during the day to go home and prepare meals, relax and also pick her kids from school during the school closing hour. Mrs. Vivian is also currently the only female rider that is active in Lokoja as at the time of this research.¹⁷

Mrs. Aisha who was the first commercial female tricycle rider stopped riding because she could not meet up with the fifteen-thousand-naira weekly payment that is meant to be remitted to the flint owner in order to pay up her hire purchase debt. Miss Blessing got married and her husband stopped her from continuing the business so she could have more time for the family. Mrs. Sandra also stopped riding because she could not meet up with the fifteen-thousand-naira weekly payment to her flint owner in order to pay up her hire purchase debt. As for MAMA, her second hand tricycle developed faults in early 2021 and she has been unable to fix it since then. This made Mrs. Vivian the only female tricycle rider that is currently active in Lokoja metropolis.¹⁸

Social Impact of Female Tricycle Riders in Lokoja

¹⁶ Interview with Comrade Adamu Shehu, TOAN Deputy State Chairman, 38 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

¹⁷ Interview with Comrade Adamu Shehu, TOAN Deputy State Chairman, 38 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

¹⁸ Interview with Comrade Adamu Shehu, TOAN Deputy State Chairman, 38 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

The involvement of women in the tricycle riding business has brought about several social impact. These social impact are discussed as follows:

Eradication of Gender Discrimination and Traditional/Societal Gender Stereotype

Gender discrimination is one of the major problems in the world today. Gender discrimination has limited a lot of women in achieving their full potentials by making them feel ‘weak, inferior and incapable’. In traditional African society, women are believed to be the care givers and are expected to stay at home to do that and also handle the home affairs, while the men are expected to be the breadwinners and to be out there in the public sphere. This traditional stereotype has limited a lot of women from reaching and achieving their goals in life. The society has ascribed certain occupation to a particular gender and many occupations are believed to be meant for the male gender and the female gender are not expected to be involved in such occupations. The transport sector is an example of such occupations as the sector is majorly dominated by the male gender. This societal stereotype has cut short the dreams of many women.¹⁹

However, with the advent of civilization, industrialization and globalization such stereotype are beginning to fade away as women are now taking up occupations that are believed to be meant for the male gender alone. The involvement of women in the transport sector has gone a long way to help eradicate traditional and societal gender stereotypes that have limited many women in life. The involvement of Mrs. Aisha in the transport system of Lokoja as the first female tricycle rider in Lokoja was like a call to action, an eye opener and an awakening for other women in Lokoja. It helped encourage other women to go into the tricycle riding business without minding the traditional and societal stereotype surrounding women’s involvement in the transport sector.²⁰

Reduction in Crime Rate

The involvement of women in the transport system has created employment opportunities for many women, thereby making the women involved to have a stable source of income. This has helped reduce crime rate as many women who would have been involved in criminal activities in order to get a source of income are now fully involved in the tricycle business, earning money on a daily basis and are able to carter for their needs without involving

¹⁹ Erik Olin, *Contemporary American Society* (New York: W.W Norton and Company, 2015), 81.

²⁰ Interview with Alhaji Idris Abdulrahman, TOAN State Chairman, 48 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

themselves in criminal activities. It is popularly said that an idle mind is the devil's workshop. According to research, 70% of those involved in criminal activities are unemployed. Therefore, the involvement of women in tricycle activities has helped to reduce the rate of criminal and illegal activities such as robbery, cyber-crime popularly known as yahoo-yahoo in Nigeria, prostitution, kidnapping, banditry, among others. It is therefore safe to say that the involvement of women in tricycle riding business has socially impacted the society in a positive way.²¹ Accordingly, more women should be encouraged or empowered to get involved, given that many of them are already encumbered and taking a break from the business already.

Reduction in Redundancy and Idleness

This is another social impact of the involvement of women in the tricycle riding business. When one is in a state of redundancy and idleness it tends to bring about a lot of problems such as low self-esteem, mental health issues as a result of worry, overthinking, depression, not being able to afford basic amenities which leads to poor standard of living, involvement in illegal and criminal activities, among others. The involvement of women in the workforce has

helped to reduce the state of redundancy and idleness as women are now very busy with their work and family which gives them little or no time to be redundant or idleness.²² When women are involved in tricycle riding business, it is a type of job that takes the whole of the day and leaves no time or space for idleness. This helps to reduce the problems that being idle can cause. This has positively affected the society as there will be more women with good, improved and better state of mental health, less women involved in criminal activities, more women who can afford their basic amenities leading to better standard of living not just for themselves but also for their families.

Reduction in the High Ratio of Drug Abuse and Addiction

Losing one's job or being unemployed has such a huge impact on a person. There is a possibility that an unemployed person can develop depression and depression is one of the major factors that causes drug addiction. A study has it that, the consumption of alcohol and hard drugs tends to go up when unemployment goes up. People feel more stressed and use hard substances so that they could cope and get through the unemployment situation they are

²¹ Interview with Alhaji Idris Abdulrahman, TOAN State Chairman, 48 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

²² Wikipedia, Women's Empowerment, https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Women's_empowerment, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

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faced with. According to the National Survey on Drug Use and Health 2005-2011, people who work more hours in a week are less likely to engage in the use of hard drugs. It is then safe to say that women who are involved in tricycle activities are less likely to be involved in the usage of hard drugs due to the long hours of work. Women who are involved in tricycle business are usually busy and buried in their work, therefore there is little or no time for them to involve themselves in drug use and abuse.²³ This is a huge positive impact to the society and the world at large.

Women Empowerment

When women are involved in the workforce, they become fully empowered. This is an essential issue as there are lesser volume of empowered women in the society compared to the volume of empowered men in the society. Though with the advent of civilisation and industrialisation, the gap is gradually being filled. When a woman is empowered with a skill or job opportunity, she is given the right to opportunities, resources, source of income, good standard of living and a

happier life. Women's empowerment equips and allows women to be better version of themselves. It helps to boost women's status and confidence, thereby eradicating depression and low self-esteem. The involvement of women in tricycle business creates women's empowerment. It provides them with a source of income, boost their confidence and takes away low-self-esteem. It closes up the workforce gap between the male and female gender, it also helps to encourage other women who might see them and also enlighten other women about the fact that women can take up any type of occupation and be good and successful at it, especially those occupations that are believed to be solely for the male gender.²⁴

²³ Recovery Ways Rehab, "Does Unemployment Cause Addictions?" www.recoveryways.com/rehab-blog, Accessed, July 2, 2022.

²⁴ Wikipedia, "Women's Empowerment" https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Women's_empowerment, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

Plate 1: A female tricycle rider. **Source:** Researchers' field work

Economic Impact of Female Tricycle Riders in Lokoja

Having discussed the social impact of female tricycle riders in Lokoja, the economic impact are discussed below.

Creation of Employment

When women are employed it provides them with a lot of opportunities and advantages. When a woman is employed, there is lesser tendency for her to be involved in illegal and criminal activities in order to earn income or eke out a

living. Being employed brings a sense of usefulness to the female gender, especially in a society that does not give recognition or importance to women in the workforce. Economically, employment provides income to poor families. It is vital to a nation's labour force, improves social welfare, and the society's well-being. The involvement of women in tricycle business has created employment for many

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

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women especially women in Lokoja which is the area of study.²⁵

Source of Income

Women's involvement in tricycle riding business provides women with a source of income. It helps women to earn a living and gives them the ability to afford basic needs such as clothing, housing, and hospital bills among others thereby improving their standard of living. It also aids them to be able to cater for their family members. Earning a living helps give women a sense of belonging and it also boost their self-confidence as well as their worth in the society. When one has a source of income, it provides them with money to spend on food, clothing, entertainment and a variety of other things. The more an individual spends, the more the demand of that products increases thereby greatly impacting the economy.²⁶

Source of Revenue for the Government

Employment creates a source of revenue for the government of every nation. One of the government's sources of revenue are taxes collected from people and corporations, used to run the nation. Although women involved in the

tricycle business are exempted from buying daily tickets which generates money for the Tricycle Owners Association of Nigeria (TOAN) to pay taxes to the government, the women still pay monthly dues to the association which is another source of income that generates money for TOAN to pay tax to the government. Therefore, the involvement of women in the tricycle business is a great source of revenue for the government which has no little impact the economy.²⁷

Increase in Productivity

Transportation plays a major role in productivity. The involvement of women in the tricycle business further enhances the movement of goods and services thereby creating an increase in productivity which largely affects the economy. With women being involved in the tricycle business, there will be more availability means of transportation compared to when men alone were involved in the tricycle business. Goods and services can be conveyed or moved

²⁵ United States Institute of Peace, "Employment Generation" <https://www.USIP.org/guiding-principles-stabilization-and-reconstruction-of-sustainable-economy>, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

²⁶ Nicolas Pologeorgis, "Employability: The Labour Force and Economy" <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/economy-employability-labour-force.asp>, Accessed, July 2, 2022.

²⁷ World Bank Revenue Dashboard, "Taxes and Government Revenue" <https://www.worldbank.org/taxes-and-government-revenue>, Accessed on 24th August, 2022.

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda

easily and faster which greatly affects productivity in terms of demand and supply.²⁸

Challenges Confronting Women in Tricycle Riding Business in Lokoja

Women in the work-force are usually faced with many challenges. Likewise, women involved in tricycle business are faced with different challenges. Some of these challenges are discussed in details below.

Hire Purchase

Most women involved in the tricycle business cannot afford to purchase their own personal tricycle (Keke NAPEP) due to its expensive price tag (of about 1.1 million naira). Most of them are on hire purchase and they make a daily, weekly or monthly return to the flint owner depending on the agreement. This daily, weekly or monthly return eats deeply into the profits they make and thereby leaves some of them with something little at the end of the day. Sometimes, some women are not able to meet up with the daily, weekly or monthly return because they cannot work into the night due to security issues. This is a great challenge for the women. The hire

purchase problem led to one of the female riders leaving the tricycle riding business.²⁹

Security Issues

Security issue is challenge faced by many women in the workforce due to their vulnerability and their emotional feature. People tend to take advantage of that, which puts women in the workforce at great danger. Women who are involved in tricycle riding business are exposed and more vulnerable to robbery attacks, kidnapping, rape and killing among others. This is why many women involved in the tricycle riding business cannot work late nights as security issues like robbery, kidnapping, rape among others, are more likely to occur during late night hours than during the daytime. This is a big challenge to the women involved in the tricycle business because it prevents them from working for longer hours and making more money.³⁰

The Work-Life Balance

The role of working women has changed throughout the world due to economic conditions and social demands. This has resulted to a scenario in which working women face

²⁸ Osita Enwe, “Organization for Economic Co-operations and Development” <https://www.Organization-for-economic-co-operations-and-development/production-and-business>, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

²⁹ Interview with Comrade Adamu Shehu, TOAN Deputy State Chairman, 38 years, Lokoja, 19th January, 2022.

³⁰ Wikipedia, “Women’s Empowerment” https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Women’s_empowerment, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

tremendous pressure to balance work and personal life. The ever increasing pressure is taking a toll on the working women, leaving them with less time for themselves. Studies shows that women in the workforce face more difficulties in balancing work life and personal life than men in the workforce. The study also shows that the reasons why women are facing more troubles maintaining a balance between work life and personal life is because of job rigidity, responsibilities related to family care, discrimination and biasness at work place and scarce family support. This is only a few among the many reasons. This work-life balance greatly affects women involved in the tricycle riding business because they are saddled with work and also the full responsibility of taking care of their homes. It prevents them from being able to spend long hours at work which affects the business or it stops them from spending enough time with their families which affects their homes.³¹

Sexual Harassment

According to research conducted at the University of Pittsburgh, the trauma of sexual

harassment leaves lasting effects on women's health, causing depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), sleep disorders, high blood pressure, anxiety and lowered self-esteem. It is sad that 7 out of every 10 women have experienced sexual harassment at their workplace.³² This does not leave out women involved in the tricycle riding business. As matter of fact women in the transport sector are considered to be one of those women who are more exposed to sexual harassment. This is due to the fact that the transport sector is filled with many thugs and touts who constantly harass women sexually at every slight opportunity. This is also one of the issues that prevents women in the transport sector from working late night hours, many are scared of being sexually harassed hence, and they retire to their house quickly even though it causes them a lot of loss as they are not able to work late night hours in order to make more profit.³³

Conclusion

This paper has examined the evolution of female tricycle riders by looking into the origin and involvement of female tricycle riders in Lokoja.

³¹ Manimekalai Kalidasen, "Work Life Balance: Issues Faced By Working Women" <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347308373-WORK-LIFE-BALANCE-ISSUES-FACED-BY-WORKING-WOMEN>, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

³² Wikipedia, "Women's Empowerment" https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Women's_empowerment, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

³³ Wikipedia, "Women's Empowerment" https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Women's_empowerment, Accessed 24th August, 2022.

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The social impact and economic impact of the involvement of female gender in the tricycle riding business as well as the challenges confronting these women were also discussed. Which has helped to shed more light on the role that women play in urban transport system especially in the tricycle riding business in Lokoja. The study concludes that women have contributed to the urban transport system in Lokoja through their involvement in commercial tricycle riding, a business sector hitherto dominated by men. This paradigm shift has demonstrated clearly that women are not petrified to take up new roles in the development of the society. Therefore, women should be encouraged to contribute their quota to the growth and development of the society in every sector of the economy.

Baba Isaac Ibrahim (Ph.D.) and Iyanuoluwa Mercy Ugbeda